

EGI Pilot Node

EGI Pilot core and exchange services integrated with the EOSC Beyond Network of Pilot Nodes

FACTSHEET FOR: Researchers; Policy makers and authorities, national; Education/training organisation/learners; Research Infrastructures

Pilot Node Profile

EGI Pilot Node – Coordinated by EGI Foundation, this federated node provides computational, storage, and authentication services to the EOSC Federation.

It integrates AAI (EGI Check-in), Infrastructure Manager for resource orchestration, and federated storage solutions, showcasing how mature EGI services can operate within the EOSC ecosystem.

Pilot Core Services

- **AAI**
Federated login to access services {production}
- **Helpdesk**
Request support {production}
- **Service Monitoring**
availability and reliability of Exchange services {production}

Pilot Exchange Services

- **EGI Check-in** (AAI)
- **EGI Infrastructure Manager** (compute)
- **EGI DataHub** (storage)
- **EGI Cloud Compute** (compute)

EOSC Beyond Core Innovation Sandbox

A pre-production environment where a large range of users, from researchers to node operators, can test the latest developments of the EOSC core.

It acts as a Federator Node offering Core Federating Capabilities for the Pilot Nodes.

User story at-a-glance

User Story 1 – Environmental Science Researcher

Persona: Researcher from an environmental science community using EOSC services.

Before: Access to computational and storage resources was fragmented, often limited to non-federated local infrastructures. Integrating datasets and compute required manual effort, slowing collaboration.

After: Through the EGI Pilot Node, researchers can deploy customised virtual environments via the **Infrastructure Manager**, access resources through **EGI Check-in**, and use **federated storage** for secure data sharing. Workflows now deploy in minutes, enhancing cross-community collaboration and reproducibility.

User Story 2 – Virtualised Storage and Data Publication

Persona: Research Infrastructure facility and data-intensive researcher.

Before: Limited online storage and complex data publication workflows hindered post-processing and sharing of experimental results.

After: With the EGI Pilot Node, users can request **virtualised storage** via **DataHub**, log in through **EOSC AAI (EGI Check-in)**, and interact via **OneData** or **Instruct FandanGO/ARIA**. Automated provisioning through the **EGI Helpdesk** enables efficient analysis and publication with DOIs and metadata in the **Research Products Catalogue**, ensuring FAIR and reproducible outcomes.

EGI Node integrations with the Core Innovation Sandox and other Pilot Nodes

Integrated Core Federating Capabilities from the Core Innovation Sandbox

- Service Catalogue
- AAI
- Discovery Hub
- Deployment Service
- Order Management

Integrated services from other Pilot Nodes

- LifeWatch ERIC
- NFDI
- INSTRUCT ERIC

Value of the Node piloting activities

The EGI Pilot Node demonstrates the tangible value of federation within EOSC Beyond by enabling researchers and Research Infrastructures to easily access and combine computational, storage, and authentication services across nodes.

By integrating mature EGI technologies such as **Check-in**, **Infrastructure Manager**, and **DataHub**, the node showcases how interoperability and automation can transform fragmented workflows into coherent, scalable research environments.

Its participation in cross-node testing validates the exchange of services and data between federated nodes, strengthening the EOSC ecosystem as a whole. For the scientific community, this means faster deployment of research environments, easier data sharing, and more reproducible results.

The EGI Pilot Node thus acts as both a proof-of-concept and a catalyst, lowering barriers to participation and providing a blueprint for future federated service providers within EOSC.

Next steps

The EGI Pilot Node will continue testing and validation activities to further strengthen interoperability within the EOSC Federation.

In parallel, efforts will focus on reinforcing the Node's identity and visibility by designing new access

structures and engagement models that enhance usability and integration for researchers and service providers.

About EOSC Beyond

www.eosc-beyond.eu

The ambition of EOSC Beyond is to support the growth of the EOSC in terms of integrated providers and active users by providing new Core technical solutions that allow developers of scientific application environments to easily compose a diverse portfolio of EOSC Resources, offering them as integrated capabilities to researchers.

Useful Links

EGI Pilot Node:

<https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/pilot/egi>

EGI webpage:

<https://www.egi.eu/>

